

Log Tracking Container-based Application Extensibility And Enhancement

August 2022

AUTHOR:

Subhashis Suara

SUPERVISOR:

Ismael Posada Trobo

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	03
<hr/>	
MOTIVATION	04
<hr/>	
PROJECT SPECIFICATION AND SUGGESTED SOLUTION	05
<hr/>	
THE DRUPAL LOG VIEWER	06
<hr/>	
MISCELLANEOUS	11
<hr/>	
FUTURE WORK	12
<hr/>	
CONCLUSION	13

INTRODUCTION

Drupal is a free, open-source software that can be used to easily create and manage websites. It consists of a content management platform and a development framework. Drupal is extensively used at CERN to build and maintain websites for CERN community and the General Public. Drupal at CERN is a customised and tailored distribution of Drupal which provides features, custom themes, and plugins among other things that are needed for an amazing website development and viewing experience.

CERN hosts around 1213 Drupal websites in total out of which, 676 are official websites and remaining websites are development instances, test instances and personal websites. Some examples of Drupal sites are Home Page of CERN (<https://home.cern>), Career opportunities (<https://careers.cern>), CMS Experiment (<https://cms.cern>) and many more sites which are used daily by thousands of people.

Figure 1. Word Cloud of CERN Websites

Just one of these websites, home.cern, saw 1.3 million unique users in July 2022 during the launch of LHC Run 3. Figure 2 shows the number of unique visitors vs date for home.cern during July 2022.

Figure 2. Number of unique visitors vs date for home.cern during July 2022

MOTIVATION

Drupal is a crucial part of the CERN web infrastructure. Being such an integral part of the CERN community, Drupal sites need constant levelling up. A key part of development and maintenance is generating and viewing logging. The motivation of this project is to build a platform for users to easily access and view logs of their Drupal sites. Prior to this project there was no easy way to access logs of Drupal sites. If someone wanted to view logs of their Drupal site, they had to either raise a ticket and request for logs, which is a tedious process, or use OpenShift to access the specific pod running the Drupal site, which is a complex process and not straightforward. Another solution that comes up in mind is to provide developers access to Kibana Dashboard in order to view logs, but Kibana doesn't have the ability to show user specific Drupal site logs (sites to which the user has access to) and instead shows logs of all Drupal sites to everyone which is undesirable. Hence, to tackle these problems, the Drupal Log Viewer was proposed to provide developers with a single platform to access and view logs of their Drupal sites.

PROJECT SPECIFICATION & SUGGESTED SOLUTION

The idea was to take an existing log viewer application built for webEOS called the webEOS log viewer and transform it into a log viewer application for Drupal sites. Since both the applications had similar end goals, the existing webEOS log viewer could be used as a blueprint for the Drupal Log Viewer. Hence, the suggested solution was to use the same architecture as the webEOS log viewer i.e., a React frontend and a PHP backend and modify each of them to create the Drupal Log Viewer.

Let's understand a basic overview of the Drupal Log Viewer platform. The logs from Drupal sites are pushed to Elasticsearch, then depending on the user's requested parameters, the PHP backend fetches specific logs from the Elasticsearch and sends the logs to React frontend for displaying the logs to the user. Figure 3 explains the basic overview of the Drupal Log Viewer platform. The detailed project work is described in the following section.

Figure 3. Data flow of logs. From left to right, Drupal site, Elasticsearch, PHP Backend, Drupal Log Viewer

DRUPAL LOG VIEWER

The Drupal Log Viewer is a platform for developers to view various types of logs of their Drupal sites. The interface consists of 2 tabs, Logs and Metrics. Let's dive deep into understanding the interface, project components and the tasks accomplished in this project.

The Logs tab contains filters for retrieving logs such as the date, from time and to time, streaming switch (to stream logs in real-time), types of logs and number of lines to display at a time. The types of logs include, NGINX access logs, NGINX error logs, PHP access logs, PHP error logs and Drupal logs. Below the filters, the interface consists of a search bar, an option to download the logs and the log viewer that displays the logs. Figure 4 is an image of the Logs tab of the Drupal Log Viewer in action.

i To report an issue or ask for assistance, contact us at [Service Desk - Drupal Service](#).
? For more general questions related to the application, we are also reachable under the [~Drupal channel in Mattermost](#) or in the [Drupal Community Forum](#).

Figure 4. Drupal Log Viewer Logs Tab

The Metrics tab contains filters for retrieving metrics such as from date and time and to date and time. Below the filters, the interface consists of a Grafana Dashboard showing various Pod metrics and PHP metrics of the Drupal site. Figure 5 is an image of the Metrics tab of the Drupal Log Viewer in action.

Figure 5. Drupal Log Viewer Metrics Tab

The project consists of a frontend folder, a backend folder, a Dockerfile that helps containerize the application and a readme file with relevant information about the project. Figure 6 shows the folder structure of the project.

```

├── backend
│   ├── debughelper.php
│   └── logviewer.php
├── Dockerfile
├── frontend
│   ├── babel.config.js
│   ├── dist
│   ├── node_modules
│   ├── package.json
│   ├── package-lock.json
│   ├── public
│   ├── src
│   ├── stylePaths.js
│   ├── tsconfig.json
│   ├── webpack.common.js
│   ├── webpack.dev.js
│   └── webpack.prod.js
└── README.md
    
```

Figure 6. Structure of Project Folder

Let's understand the components of the React frontend. Figure 7 shows the folder structure of the React frontend.

```

├── App.css
├── App.js
├── App.test.js
├── components
│   ├── CustomLogViewer.jsx
│   ├── Metrics.jsx
│   └── useWindowSize.js
├── index.css
├── index.js
├── react-app-env.d.ts
├── reportWebVitals.js
├── setupTests.js
└── utils.js

```

Figure 7. Structure of Frontend Folder

Some of the important components of the frontend are App.js, CustomLogViewer.jsx and Metrics.jsx. App.js is the wrapper of the platform that consists of the header, the page content, and the footer. The header consists of the title of the application and username of the user that is signed in. The page content consists of the CustomLogViewer.jsx and Metrics.jsx components in form of Tabs.

CustomLogViewer.jsx is the component responsible for the Logs tab and Metrics.jsx is the component responsible for the Metrics tab. The footer contains links for support regarding the log viewer application. Some of tasks that were done for frontend development are as follows:

- **Update the dependencies:** All the dependencies of the frontend were smoothly updated to their latest version except the @pattern/react-core dependency. Updating @pattern/react-core dependency from v4.175.4 to v4.221.3, the latest version, broke the application. After debugging it was found that the alignment attribute of ToolbarItem broke the app and removing the attribute fixed the application without any visual changes to the application.
- **Make Toolbar Responsive:** The toolbar containing the filters was not responsive. To make the toolbar responsive, a custom react hook called useWindowSize.js was added. Based on the values of the window size obtained using the custom react hook, the toolbar was made responsive.
- **Implement Log Downloading Functionality:** Functionality to download logs was implemented for a specific day and time duration with appropriate name for the log file.
- **Create Metrics Tab:** A Metrics tab was created with a toolbar for date filters and an embedded Grafana Dashboard to display the Drupal site metrics. The embedding was done using an iframe and the dashboard is controlled using the parameters of the URL given to the iframe i.e., from and to datetime, refresh interval (5 secs) and view mode (kiosk). Following changes were made to the Grafana Operator to make this feature possible:

```

security:
  allow_embedding: true
  cookie_samesite: none
  cookie_secure: true

```


- **Add "Signed in as: username" in the header:** A component was added to the header of the application that displayed the current user that is signed in. To implement this feature, a field called username was created in the backend response. This feature can help users with multiple accounts identify the account they are using while accessing the Drupal Log Viewer. Figure 8 shows how this component looks.

Figure 8. "Signed in as: username" Component on Top Right of Header

- **Updated Date and Time Validators:** Some quality-of-life improvements were added to the date and time validators. Following were the improvements:
 - If the date/time is invalid in any case (including being later or earlier than supposed to), the dropdown doesn't close hence, forcing the user to make corrections to date or/and time.
 - Created calendarDateRangeValidator to allow the latest day selectable (in calendar) as the current day and warn users if they try to set a day later than the current day.
 - Warnings and errors are now shown as toast notifications. Figure 9 shows a toast notification in action.

Figure 9. Warning Notification Toast

Let's understand the components of the PHP backend. There is only one file called logviewer.php that handles all the frontend requests. The backend validates the request parameters, authenticates the user with an access token that is forwarded by the OpenShift OAuth Proxy, and ensures that the user has the appropriate permission for the Drupal site requested. Once all the checks are done, the backend then builds a Elasticsearch query with all the provided user parameters and sends the request to the relevant Elasticsearch endpoint. The data response from the Elasticsearch pipes through a data builder function in the backend that packages the response as required by the frontend and sends the response to the frontend for the users to view the logs. Some of tasks that were done for backend development are as follows:

- **Deciding Data Points:** The webOS Log Viewer used a set of parameters to fetch the logs from Elasticsearch. These parameters had to be changed for the Drupal Log Viewer. After discussion, it was decided that the Drupal Log Viewer would use 2 parameters to fetch the appropriate logs, project (namespace) and Drupal site. The project data point already existed, but the Drupal site data point had to be injected into the logs which made fetching the logs by the user's Drupal site possible.

- **Upgrade PHP version:** PHP version was updated from 7.4 to 8.1 since, PHP 7.4 was reaching end of life and was going to lose all support starting November 2022. Following changes were made for the transition:
 - Converted json_decode object to array in filter_var_array function for \$_POST variable.
 - Changed parameter filters from FILTER_SANITIZE_STRING to FILTER_SANITIZE_FULL_SPECIAL_CHARS as the former filter is deprecated.
- **Check Elasticsearch Calls Using Curl and Integrate them into the Backend:** The Elasticsearch endpoint was tested with different queries using curl in order to get appropriate responses. The necessary Elasticsearch calls were then integrated into the backend. Following indexes were made available to the user i.e., nginx-access, nginx-error, drupal-logs, php-access, php-error.
- **Implement API Authorization:** API authorization was implemented which ensured that the user had the appropriate permission to access the required Drupal site logs. GetSiteUrl function was changed to point to the correct OpenShift API endpoint, and the function was modified for returning relevant data/error.

Hence, this was an overview of the Drupal Log Viewer, its components and the tasks that were accomplished during the summer.

MISCELLANEOUS

The idea of Metrics tab was to make it convenient for the users to view the metrics of their Drupal site in the same platform as the Drupal Log Viewer. Metrics tab shows various pieces of information such as pod metric i.e., PHP memory, NGINX memory, storage, CPU usage, memory usage, number of connections, average response time etc and PHP metrics i.e., total PHP process utilisation, accepted connections, queued requests, requests per process, number of active and idle processes, total process utilisation and container termination etc. The Metrics tab uses the Grafana dashboard from the Grafana service at CERN. The dashboard is fetched from the Grafana service and displayed in the Metrics tab using an iframe. The user parameters provided in the Metrics filters such as date and time for fetching metrics are sent to the Grafana dashboard using URL parameters in the iframe src attribute. Hence, this is an overview of how the Metrics tab works using the Grafana service at CERN.

A visual bug was reported by a user of the webEOS Log Viewer which changed the look and feel of the application in production compared to development. This was bug carried over to the Drupal Log Viewer as well. The bug was resolved as a part of this project fixing it for both the webEOS Log Viewer and the Drupal Log Viewer. The issue was caused due to the way the application was built while transitioning from development to production. Building the application using npm build changed the look and feel of the application due to missing fonts and visual elements. The visual bug was fixed by adding the webpack configurations used in the [patternfly react seed project](#) and using the webpack build method instead of the npm build method. Figure 10 shows a before and after of the bug being fixed.

Figure 10. Before (Top Image) and After (Bottom Image) the Visual Bug was Fixed

FUTURE WORK

The Drupal Log Viewer platform was successfully developed over the course of summer. There are more things that can be done to improve this project. Some of the ideas are listed as follows:

- **Implement the Drupal Log Viewer into the Web Services Portal:** The idea is to add a log viewer button to the Drupal site management page in the Web Services Portal. When the user clicks on this button, the Drupal Log Viewer opens in a new tab. The Drupal Log Viewer shows logs for the same site that the user had opened in the Web Services Portal.
- **Add multi-days log viewing and downloading functionality:** Currently, the log viewer shows logs of only one day and has the option to download logs for only one day. A feature extension can be to allow users to view and download logs over a multiple number of days at a time.
- **Add notifications for events happening in Grafana:** The Grafana dashboard has various types of graphs, gauges, and other pieces of information. There can be a feature that notifies the user about the Grafana dashboard events using toast notifications. The notifications can be new events, threshold-based notifications from gauges etc.
- **Provide the ability for users to use their own Grafana custom graphs:** The Grafana dashboard displays a predefined set of graphs, gauges, and pieces of information for all the Drupal sites. A nice addition to the project would be to allow users to use their own custom Grafana graphs in the Grafana dashboard.

CONCLUSION

Over the summer, the project successfully accomplished its goal of creating a Drupal log and metrics viewing platform for the CERN community. Completing the project taught me more about Drupal, OpenShift, React.js, Patternfly Framework, PHP, Kibana, and Docker which helped me hone my skills. I couldn't have done it without the support and guidance of my mentor Mr. Ismael. I am grateful to the CERN IT Department for providing me this opportunity and the experience of a lifetime.